

PCA Scores Report

Experiment : Tutti VS Tutti

Active entity list : Oneway ANOVA p (Corr) cut-off = 0.05 TUTTI VS TUTTI

Color by Trattamento

6PP	76A	BIO	BIO+6PP	BIO+76A
BIO+T22	BIO+T22+76A	CTRL	T22	T22+76A

Description

Algorithm: Principal Components Analysis

Parameters:

Column indices = [1-90]

Pruning option = [numPrincipalComponents, [4]]

Mean centered = true

Scale = true

3-D scores = true

PCA on = Columns

Samples	Component 1 (20.06%)	Component 2 (13.8%)	Component 3 (12.78%)	Component 4 (7.97%)
6PP_R1_1	6.246289	0.7156512	7.2278595	3.900745
6PP_R1_2	6.2410917	0.747945	7.2606707	4.050989
6PP_R1_3	6.121351	0.90534943	7.027438	3.8907683
6PP_R2_1	3.0416808	1.5372086	4.370244	0.3890545
6PP_R2_2	1.9383745	1.081022	3.6790497	-0.24482785
6PP_R2_3	2.0786896	1.1211718	3.741459	-0.058628038
6PP_R3_1	4.7226057	1.6065282	6.7286334	2.2357168
6PP_R3_2	4.71599	1.7535125	6.9361386	2.11254
6PP_R3_3	5.3068967	1.9333341	7.336566	2.3716552
76A_R1_1	6.836961	-2.4390295	4.641	-0.8872089
76A_R1_2	6.9086347	-2.4909267	4.979968	-0.7371339
76A_R1_3	6.82053	-2.4266605	4.8941216	-0.8698779
76A_R2_1	1.0614727	-0.9744638	1.1507674	-5.166447
76A_R2_2	0.79767567	-1.5932708	1.0976146	-5.45509
76A_R2_3	1.1472044	-1.0319262	1.2193208	-5.203888
76A_R3_1	6.0642524	-1.7707573	4.9718113	-0.86874306
76A_R3_2	6.272549	-2.1583743	5.309102	-0.9204269
76A_R3_3	6.2374706	-2.0044327	5.56414	-1.0431281
BIO_R1_1	0.019787759	7.7781477	-4.206401	0.07673628
BIO_R1_2	0.21973628	7.8209004	-3.8200862	0.14021716
BIO_R1_3	0.08015612	7.6715736	-4.2497244	-0.06299803
BIO_R2_1	-0.95212626	8.763659	-4.9445505	-0.63060135
BIO_R2_2	-1.1797484	8.743347	-4.9219646	-0.94254017
BIO_R2_3	-0.7797696	8.976519	-4.761305	-0.58805776
BIO_R3_1	3.153009	8.737278	0.48192382	3.334932
BIO_R3_2	2.791061	8.56434	0.32382917	3.0259771
BIO_R3_3	2.7439818	8.583378	0.35125235	3.0914197
BIO+6PP_R1_1	-1.073553	-6.0824404	-4.595203	4.244213
BIO+6PP_R1_2	-1.325137	-6.10397	-4.767503	4.187192
BIO+6PP_R1_3	-0.9464052	-5.8918962	-4.257477	4.334264
BIO+6PP_R2_1	-4.650321	-6.4943757	-7.346481	2.220016
BIO+6PP_R2_2	-4.735728	-6.4756284	-7.4847426	2.0030766
BIO+6PP_R2_3	-4.7791348	-6.6145606	-7.3735704	2.0022354
BIO+6PP_R3_1	1.778946	-6.817934	-1.2615988	6.5634694
BIO+6PP_R3_2	1.8524224	-6.7898164	-1.594477	6.805936
BIO+6PP_R3_3	1.7635885	-6.6702905	-1.6193458	6.8447065
BIO+76A_R1_1	-2.1692455	-6.603666	-2.4475985	1.2256889
BIO+76A_R1_2	-1.9354436	-6.5689836	-2.1398532	1.290922
BIO+76A_R1_3	-2.1306362	-6.635927	-2.3480062	1.2278464
BIO+76A_R2_1	0.1932978	-5.1848745	-0.992457	2.2761316
BIO+76A_R2_2	0.085735865	-5.224483	-0.99164104	2.2898595
BIO+76A_R2_3	-0.316676	-5.4392715	-1.4666564	2.0455012
BIO+76A_R3_1	-0.6957509	-5.183744	-0.4273693	2.686831
BIO+76A_R3_2	-0.74751437	-5.1714377	-0.46790278	2.654873
BIO+76A_R3_3	-0.76814634	-5.2134113	-0.6148999	2.5732837
BIO+T22_R1_1	-1.0082451	0.5498123	-5.129073	-2.0952637
BIO+T22_R1_2	-1.4811847	0.25298932	-5.585514	-2.4144225

Samples	Component 1 (20.06%)	Component 2 (13.8%)	Component 3 (12.78%)	Component 4 (7.97%)
BIO+T22_R1_3	-1.4162282	0.4926605	-5.4906926	-2.432537
BIO+T22_R2_1	1.8325396	1.3349054	-1.8798957	0.87256217
BIO+T22_R2_2	1.7781721	0.8744041	-1.5057538	0.8674733
BIO+T22_R2_3	1.9333768	0.96093285	-1.4948655	0.85292834
BIO+T22_R3_1	1.0361209	-0.34815443	-2.5817897	-0.52072173
BIO+T22_R3_2	0.26202378	-0.66695166	-3.4064033	-0.9124348
BIO+T22_R3_3	0.010273713	-0.792614	-3.6157286	-1.0461355
BIO+T22+76A_R1_1	0.7906136	4.790103	-3.9247649	0.12778564
BIO+T22+76A_R1_2	0.57296115	4.800409	-4.030986	-0.0068179406
BIO+T22+76A_R1_3	0.6612603	4.667421	-4.0867987	0.02864967
BIO+T22+76A_R2_1	3.3444803	4.898873	-1.8575051	1.7070495
BIO+T22+76A_R2_2	3.1332362	4.8657875	-1.8814467	1.5553122
BIO+T22+76A_R2_3	3.6900282	4.8932204	-1.6387409	1.8228751
BIO+T22+76A_R3_1	-1.230726	4.959342	-5.776375	-1.3629875
BIO+T22+76A_R3_2	-0.7949237	5.179613	-5.307314	-1.1672755
BIO+T22+76A_R3_3	-1.2332535	5.0632086	-5.636975	-1.3890152
C_R1_1	4.5467257	-3.6747842	4.4238462	-5.8199577
C_R1_2	5.0025725	-3.7909374	3.6746752	-5.940308
C_R1_3	4.596621	-3.9957366	3.2544725	-6.0307817
C_R2_1	2.5320299	-3.2449193	0.06169995	-7.0146422
C_R2_2	2.79851	-3.073745	0.31579924	-7.0376897
C_R2_3	2.8765132	-2.7894294	0.2731427	-7.0569763
C_R3_1	0.8775982	-3.0637596	-0.9962217	-8.693834
C_R3_2	0.7284874	-3.275849	-0.99239415	-8.796034
C_R3_3	0.63037956	-3.3969595	-1.0989572	-8.790859
T22_R1_1	4.918301	1.2005694	1.3566172	3.0666502
T22_R1_2	4.7773194	1.1816489	1.0537612	2.9857435
T22_R1_3	5.017435	1.3251905	1.423447	3.0947125
T22_R2_1	-0.4823057	1.6795317	-2.8759096	-0.9669134
T22_R2_2	-0.6116001	1.6146151	-2.8116271	-1.1730717
T22_R2_3	-0.5790547	1.5856625	-2.7353978	-1.0972395
T22_R3_1	0.78105456	1.153677	-1.5894278	0.38988242
T22_R3_2	1.4672272	1.5826813	-0.912279	0.589624
T22_R3_3	1.5051718	1.5448945	-0.57624805	0.5233132
T22+76A_R1_1	-16.37821	0.25834933	3.1408515	-1.6953592
T22+76A_R1_2	-16.200323	0.43276173	3.778142	-1.4070212
T22+76A_R1_3	-16.597343	0.36163154	3.34071	-1.5992334
T22+76A_R2_1	-12.62715	1.6957836	6.8625426	0.6796377
T22+76A_R2_2	-13.2394	1.5084175	6.4801483	0.45501295
T22+76A_R2_3	-12.552225	1.8434556	7.298755	0.6225643
T22+76A_R3_1	-10.543623	1.3873012	8.12892	1.5037681
T22+76A_R3_2	-11.976678	0.9090037	6.98854	1.0426507
T22+76A_R3_3	-11.204452	1.2808015	7.3713355	1.262359